

KICHIK BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA INFRATUZILMA FAOLIYATIDAN FOYDALANISHNING ENG DOLZARB MASALALARI

THE MOST URGENT ISSUES OF THE USE OF INFRASTRUCTURE ACTIVITIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESS AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP

НАИБОЛЕЕ АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ИНФРАСТРУКТУРНЫХ МЕРОПРИЯТИЙ В РАЗВИТИИ МАЛОГО БИЗНЕСА И ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСТВА

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ANNOTATSIIYA

Shubhasiz, davlat kichik va o'rta biznesni qo'llab-quvvatlovchi infratuzilmaga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatadi va davlat bu ta'sirning asosi bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Hozirda infratuzilmani rivojlantirish agentliklarining tarkibiy qismlari qanday ishlashini muvofiqlashtirish va boshqarish uchun taklif etilayotgan qonunlar, dasturlar va farmoyishlar ishlab chiqilmoqda. Shu bilan birga, hududlarda infratuzilmani rivojlantirish loyihalari qonun chiqaruvchi organlar tomonidan boshqariladi va ijro etuvchi organlar ko'zni rivojlantirish sohasidagi davlat siyosatini amalga oshirishda bevosita yoki bilvosita ishtirok etadilar, bu ularni infratuzilma institutlari deb hisoblash huquqiga ega.

ANNOTATION

Obviously, the state has a significant influence on the infrastructure supporting small and medium-sized businesses, and the state serves as the basis of this influence. Proposed laws, programs, and ordinances are currently being developed to coordinate and govern how the components of infrastructure development agencies operate. However, infrastructure development projects in the regions are managed by legislative bodies, and executive bodies are directly or indirectly involved in the implementation of state policy in the field of SME development, which has the right to consider them as infrastructure institutions.

АННОТАЦИЯ

Очевидно, что государство оказывает значительное влияние на инфраструктуру, поддерживающую малый и средний бизнес, и государство служит основой этого влияния. В настоящее время разрабатываются предлагаемые законы, программы и постановления для координации и регулирования деятельности компонентов агентств по развитию инфраструктуры. Однако проектами развития инфраструктуры в регионах управляют законодательные органы, а исполнительные органы прямо или косвенно участвуют в реализации государственной политики в области развития малого и среднего бизнеса, что имеет право рассматривать их как инфраструктурные институты.

KALIT SO'ZLAR

iqtisodiy rivojlanish, ko'k, infratuzilma, resurs salohiyati, mintaqa, yumshoq infratuzilma, qattiq infratuzilma

KEYWORDS

economic development, SME, infrastructure, resource potential, region, soft infrastructure, hard infrastructure

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА

экономическое развитие, малый и средний бизнес, инфраструктура, ресурсный потенциал, регион, мягкая инфраструктура, жесткая инфраструктура

INTRODUCTION

Achieving economic development in the regions is closely related to the development of small business and entrepreneurship and the formation of conditions and infrastructure that meet the requirements of the times and continuous improvement. Today, one of the main directions of socio-economic development in our country is the development of small business and entrepreneurship in the regions and the creation of appropriate infrastructure.

Infrastructure is one of the factors that ensure entrepreneurship, thereby the state economy and the well-being of society. Therefore, important measures have been taken in recent years in our country to develop small business and entrepreneurship in the regions and to create the necessary infrastructure for it.

This formulation of the question requires solving a number of methodological and methodological problems, in particular, defining the main concepts for this study. In economic research, the most common category for describing the resource endowment of an area is the category of "resource potential". At present, different approaches are proposed in the interpretation of the concept of "resource potential of the region".

The existence of the structural nature of the economic unit "region" allows defining it as a system consisting of many elements that are related and connected to each other, forming a certain unity under the influence of a basic factor. The development of the territory, ensuring its integrity, forming a network structure, interaction with the external environment is also related to the existence of the system-forming factor, which, in our opinion, is the main infrastructure that activates all other areas. provides an opportunity to create infrastructures and sustainable economic and, therefore, social development.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Entrepreneurship infrastructure concept to understand primarily for infrastructure _ sure

tariff analyze important The term " infrastructure " is from the 20th century the first from half starting from military of technique specialized devices description for used (Lemer , 1992, Tan and etc. 2000). USA like industry developed the term "infrastructure" in countries the first times international in the press in the 1980s appeared. Since then since the government in hand has been all assets industry in the sector infrastructure that is called. In general, when people this word when they heard hard¹ infrastructure about to think preferred they see , for example, roads, iron roads, electricity stations, telecommunications, wide striped communications, tunnels, industry parks and others. Tan and others (2000), infrastructures known one of the region features cover receiver separately location as determines. From this except infrastructure economic of growth basis it is corporate the landscape change and in the end access obstacles decrease can, indeed, many scholars have defined business infrastructure as the material requirements for the functioning of a business or society. Infrastructure components undoubtedly make people's daily tasks easier. In a broader sense, infrastructure means, in particular, the main elements or components that support the full range of business activities and help open business prospects in a completely different area (Flora C.B. and Frola J.L., 1993; Macke and Markley, 2006; Audretsch, Heger, & Veit, 2014). Infrastructures usually consist of buildings that are managed and constructed by a local government or administration, so they fall under the category of public assets. Infrastructure plays a crucial role in the economic prosperity of a country. Both physical and non-physical infrastructure are considered in the idea of entrepreneurial infrastructure (Brenes and Haar, 2012; Macke and Markley, 2006).

Tan et al.'s (2000) definition of entrepreneurial infrastructure is adopted to avoid confusion regarding the term entrepreneurial infrastructure in relation to entrepreneurs. The

¹ Many foreign scientists have interpreted infrastructure into soft and hard types.

concept of business infrastructure includes all the facilities and services available in any specific geographic jurisdiction to encourage the development of new enterprises as well as the expansion of existing or small and medium-sized enterprises. In other words, the general idea of industrial infrastructure elements is divided into a category called "entrepreneur".

Business infrastructure main disadvantage is that it is the same definition have not _ However , his parts or categories between very less similarity there is With that together , his parts or groups between to each other similarity less _ Brenes and Haar (2012) their innovative in the analyses hard from the infrastructure out coming out five basic soft infrastructure existence , including to business help show services , family of business harmony , state offices by financial support _ help and information services use opportunity existence shows . According to Samli (2011) , entrepreneurship of infrastructure There are six types : intellectual (education or human capital), physical (roads , railway roads , airports , cars ways and others), high technological (telecommunications , internet), and main infrastructure (water , energy supply giver or electricity energy). In fact, He and Nee (2004) entrepreneurship for of infrastructure four element offer does: services and technical support, financial help , information and expertise.

Macro level of the area infrastructures separated following groups:

- digging receiver industry infrastructures : oil , gas, mining , coal , rare soil , construction raw materials , wood preparation ;
- energy infrastructures : hydropower (hydroelectric power plant), nuclear power plant (NPP), heat energy (IES), gas station (GES), mobile energy, alternative energy;
- work release infrastructures : mechanical engineering, wood again work, chemistry, industry and medicine, petrochemical, metallurgy, construction, automobile industry, shipbuilding, aircraft industry, agro- industry, agriculture farm;

- social infrastructure: medicine institutions, general education, sports, social, cultural, housing and communal services, local authority, tourism and tourism, judiciary;

- communication infrastructure: mail, mobile communication, radiotelephone, general information (public information means, internet, radio, television);

- innovative infrastructures: academic (RAS), scientific research (research institutes), higher profession education (universities), secondary profession education, higher education (colleges), consulting, technology park, engineering ;

- financial infrastructures: budget (treasury, pension, tax), banking, insurance, shares (enterprises, mutual funds, private pension funds), stock exchange finance, customs;

- the market infrastructures : retail trade, wholesale trade, commodity exchange, general eating;

- transport infrastructure: automobile, railway road, highway pipe, sea, river (internal water), aviation, space, telecommunications (incl. electricity transmission lines - electric transmission lines).

of territories economic growth possibilities work release to the process attraction to be done possible has been of resources quantity and quality with is determined. Many of scientists studies work release process and work release with resource provide territorial such as localization (region, municipality) problems seeing to exit is directed. In the area small business and entrepreneurship development opportunities determine, relevant of the area resources and infrastructural potential assessment requirement is enough.

METHODOLOGY

In this chapter, we conduct an econometric analysis of indicators of socio-economic infrastructure affecting the activity of small and medium-sized business entities. For this, it is necessary to determine the statistical and econometric interaction of the factors

representing the socio-economic infrastructure and forming their basis.

The external impact of social infrastructure is significant. Social marginal productivity (SMP) is superior to private marginal productivity for social goods such as education and health. Therefore, private financing of such social infrastructure may be less than required. Therefore, the government should immediately provide funds and other necessary resources to

implement such social infrastructure initiatives. Social infrastructure does not have to be managed or controlled by the government, but the government should set policies and monitor how they are implemented.

We have discussed in detail about social infrastructure and its impact on K&B in previous chapters. Now let's talk about the factors representing the social infrastructure and used in our econometric model and their features.

1- table

Analysis for variables description²

No	Variables	Variable description
1	Y	Number of small and medium business enterprises, in units
2	X2	Labor force efficiency , coef.
3	X3	Hospitals together _
4	X4	Number of crimes , in units
5	X5	Number of graduates , in units
6	X6	The share of households supplied with natural gas , in %
7	X7	The share of households supplied with drinking water , in %
8	X8	Electricity production , mln. kw t _
9	X9	to the Internet connected number of enterprises , in units
10	X10	Underground resources that can be mined in the regions amount , ml rd . in sum
11	X11	Freight turnover in the regions , thousand tons
12	X12	The number of passengers transported in the regions , in units
13	X13	Commercial to small and medium businesses investments directed by banks, bln. soum

2-table

General characteristics of the factors used in the model

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
LGBT	168	9.515088	.5591861	8.478661	11.35846
LNATRES	154	4.409674	2.692085	-3.506558	9.478671

²Statistical analysis software Stata 15 was developed by the author

LCRIME	168	8.52485	.5974878	7.13966	10.14812
LFREIGHT	168	10.69085	.9019609	8.619389	12.73803
LPASSENGER	168	8.835506	1.030577	7.302073	16.08554
LGRADUATE	168	8.197838	.7360044	6.761573	10.47858
LELECTR	144	6.00282	3.298795	-4.60517	9.905965
INVEST	168	6.382558	4.838192	.7	27.76657
INTERNET	98	21.9551	7.460274	8	44.5
DENSITY	168	709.3637	1813.672		7699.6
Water	168	75.49762	15.01685	34.8	100
GAS	168	68.65357	20.24168		99.9

Since the sampling was done before the statistical committee examined these indicators, we believe that there is no bias in the methods used to determine the existing small businesses and entrepreneurs in the regions and the impact of infrastructure on their activities.

Y=

$$\beta_0 + \beta_1 lenergy + \beta_2 lnatres + \beta_3 lcrime + \beta_4 lfreight + \beta_5 lpassen + \beta_6 lgraduate + \beta_7 gas + \beta_8 water + \beta_9 density + \beta_{10} internet + \beta_{11} investment + \beta_{12} laborprod + \beta_{13} hospital + \mu_i + \delta_i \quad (1)$$

The first-difference tool is used in the econometric model of the study because it is easy to correct for serial autocorrelations in the annual report data. We also use fixed effects equations to compare which instrument best describes the model. Proceeding with the analysis without testing the factors covered in the model can lead

We create an econometric model using the selected variables. The main goal of the dissertation is how various infrastructural factors affect the growth of small and medium-sized businesses in different regions of Uzbekistan. Therefore, we used the number of K&BT as a dummy variable to determine the effects.

to autocorrelation and ultimately biased results, so we use a case-first model-testing approach to address this issue. To do this, we measure the log factor of the number of enterprises, the ratio of the independent variables representing the infrastructure in the method of least squares.

3-table

OLS regression of the model

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs = 79.00	
				F(13, 65) = 89.93	
Model	21.1010615	13	1.62315858	Prob > F = 0.0000	
Residual	1.17316319	65	.018048664	R-squared = 0.9473	
				Adj R-squared = 0.9368	
Total	22.2742247	78	.285566983	Root MSE = .13435	
LGBT	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P>t	[95% Conf. Interval]

LENERGY	.0354339	.0066903 5.30	0.000	.0220725	.0487953
LNATRES	.0028459	.0108703 0.26	0.794	-.0188635	.0245553
LCRIME	.1476154	.0535993 2.75	0.008	.0405703	.2546605
LFRIEGHT	.0814909	.0405586 2.01	0.049	.0004899	.162492
LPASSEN	-.0183116	.0229971 -0.80	0.429	-.0642401	.0276168
LGRADUATE	-.0155989	.0327508 -0.48	0.635	-.0810068	.0498091
GAS	.0018741	.0010399 1.80	0.076	-.0002027	.0039509
WATER	-.0094098	.0016416 -5.73	0.000	-.0126884	-.0061312
DENSITY	.000123	.0000168 7.32	0.000	.0000895	.0001566
INTERNET	-.0234114	.0040779 -5.74	0.000	-.0315555	-.0152672
INVEST	-.002742	.0044697 -0.61	0.542	-.0116686	.0061846
LABORPROD	.0072184	.0015743 4.59	0.000	.0040743	.0103625
HOSPITAL	.0103042	.0008342 12.35 p.m	0.000	.0086382	.0119703
_cons	7.564228	.4611533 16.40	0.000	6.643241	8.485215

There are two types of multicollinearity:

Non-strict multicollinearity, full multicollinearity and exact multicollinearity (also called partial). If there is an exact linear relationship between the variables of the model, or if one independent variable can be written exactly linearly in terms of another independent variable, this is called strict multicollinearity.

For example, imagine that when creating a macroeconomic model, exports, imports, and net exports are considered as variables. When all these three factors are included in the model, it shows that the explanatory variables of the model are expressed linearly through each other, since net exports are equal to the difference between exports and imports.

From the above definition and example, it is clear how to solve the problem of strict multicollinearity. For this, take the second variable. For example, if the model already accounts for imports and exports, adding net exports obviously does not contribute new information, and this third factor can easily be discarded.

In the case of pure multicollinearity, modern econometric software automatically removes one of the linearly dependent variables, making least squares prediction computationally feasible.

When there is a strong correlation between the independent variables, but no clear linear relationship, this is known as partial multicollinearity. Thus, they are "almost" linearly related, but not very strongly linearly dependent on each other. The precision of the coefficient values is low and the standard errors of the coefficient values are significant in the presence of partial multicollinearity. This is because if two independent variables in a model are strongly correlated, they often change at the same time and it is difficult to isolate their effect on the independent variable. Therefore, the decrease in the accuracy of the calculation of individual coefficients is the main negative effect of multicollinearity.

Variance inflation factor, or short VIF , is a multiplier that increases variance. This indicates an increase in variance in the univariate regression scenario. If the variables are orthogonal, then $VIF_j = 1$ and $R_j^2 = 0$, respectively, and the significance of the variables is non-decreasing from each other. In contrast, if there is a linear relationship $R_j^2 = 1$ or clear multicollinearity $VIF_j = +\infty$, the variance of the coefficients will also be infinite. As we have already mentioned, it is difficult to correctly analyze the regression in this situation.

According to economists, if any of the variables $VIF_j > 10$ If, multicollinearity exists in

the regression equation. This number is also mentioned in Gujarati textbook. Quasi-multicollinearity, according to some critical theory, is not a theoretical issue. Since they are

ignorant of econometrics, there are no methods for establishing specific critical values or establishing protocols for evaluating hypotheses about its existence or not.

4-table

VIF test results

Variables	VIF	1/ VIF
LFREIGHT	5.01	0.199541
POPULATION	4.46	0.224167
HOSPITAL	4.17	0.239797
INTERNET	4.08	0.245252
CRIME	4.07	0.245444
LRESOURCE	3.63	0.275386
WATER	3.56	0.280922
LMEH	3.12	0.320391
Graduate	2.45	0.408252
LETTER	2.28	0.439130
LENERGY	2.01	0.497059
GAS	1.99	0.502463
INVEST	1.81	0.552506
Mean VIF	3.28	

It can be seen that this indicator is not higher than 10 in any of the variables used in the model. This means that the variables in our model do not have the problem of multicollinearity and are correctly selected.

In econometrics, the term "heteroscedasticity" refers to the heterogeneity of observations represented by the non-uniform (non-constant) variance of the random error of a regression model. The opposite of homoscedasticity, which refers to the homogeneity of the data and the consistency of the model's random error variance, is heteroscedasticity. Due to the heteroscedasticity of the random errors, least squares estimates are inefficient.

In this case, the traditional estimate of the covariance matrix of least squares parameter estimation also proves to be unreliable and inaccurate. Thus, statistical conclusions about the accuracy of the obtained estimates may not be

sufficient. In this context, testing models for heteroscedasticity is one of the important steps in building econometric models.

Goldfeld-Quandt, Park, Glaser, White, Brush-Pagan, and Sperman rank correlation tests, among others, can be used to determine the presence of heteroskedasticity in random residuals. If the random residuals are assumed to be normally distributed and the observations are sufficient, the Goldfeld-Quandt test is used.

One way to detect heteroskedasticity using graphical analysis is to create a scatterplot of independent variables on the **Y-axis and one of the regression coefficients on the X-axis**. Analysis of the plot of the regression residuals provides an additional selection. Residuals are plotted against each explanatory variable in ascending order.

If the variance of the residuals near zero is the same (for example, as in Fig.), we can assume that there is no heteroscedasticity

associated with this regressor in the data. If a plot of residuals clearly shows that the value of the regressor affects the dispersion of the residuals

around zero, then heteroscedasticity is present (eg, as in Fig.-1)

1- fig. Location of points where heteroscedasticity does not exist.

2- fig. Location of points where heteroscedasticity exists.

Appropriate formal statistical tests can be useful in addition to studying the graphs, as it is not always possible to determine with certainty whether heteroscedasticity is present or not. The following list includes the two most popular tests.

Breusch-Pagan test

The absence of heteroscedasticity in the equation is the hypothesis tested in this test.

$$H_0 : \sigma_1^2 = \dots = \sigma_n^2$$

An alternative theory suggests that a set of variables somehow affects how random errors change:

$$H_1 : \sigma_i^2 = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1 z_i^{(1)} + \dots + \gamma_l$$

(2)

Here is $z_i^{(1)}, z_i^{(2)}, \dots, z_i^{(p)}$ a list of variables expected to affect the variation in random error. These variables are usually taken as the regressors of the original model and their least squares.

We also use the Breusch-Pagan and Skynes-Kurtosis test to determine the presence of heteroskedasticity in our model. The content of the null hypothesis of this test states that there is no heteroscedasticity in the model, while the alternative hypothesis states that there is heteroscedasticity. It can be seen that the r-value of the obtained results is higher than 0.05, which requires us to reject the alternative hypothesis and accept the null hypothesis.

From the obtained test results, we can conclude that our model and all the selected variables are of good quality and do not have any

negative influence on each other. Therefore, we can use the selected factors in subsequent models without hesitation.

Source	chi2	df	R
Heteroskedasticity	79.00	78.00	0.4471
Skewness	7.15	13 . 00	0.8945
Kurtosis	2.36	1.00	0.1246
Total	88.50	92.00	0.5838

Since we have formed a panel database in this study, we only use econometric models that can effectively analyze this database.

Results and discussions

Undoubtedly, one of the most widely used approaches in quantitative social research is structural equation modeling (SEM model). The depth of the underlying statistical theory, the ability to answer important substantive problems, and the availability of software specifically designed for systemic equation modeling, as well as the ease of use, can be considered the main reasons for its appeal. Despite the popularity of this method , it can be argued that its "first-generation" use has become entrenched in conventional practice, hindering both meaningful and statistical gains.

Model analysis, often referred to as structural equation modeling (SEM), is a multivariate technique used to evaluate theories about interactions between different variables. Its origins date back to the 1920s, when it was created to measure and analyze unidirectional causal relationships in genetic data.

SEM - A linear model modified in several ways, as shown in Fig.: the coupling matrix, "trimmed" to include only important directions. Self-connections are strictly prohibited. Responses from appropriate geographic areas and possibly experimental or bilinear terms are

The independent variables are calculated using the sample covariance system of the data instead of minimizing the sum of squared errors.

included in the data matrix Y . The general linear model serves as the basic model:

(3)

$$[y_t^1 \ y_t^2 \ y_t^3] = [y_t^1 \ y_t^2 \ y_t^3] \begin{bmatrix} 0 & b_{12} & b_{13} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & b_{32} & 0 \end{bmatrix} + \epsilon_t$$

(4)

$$Y = Y\beta + \epsilon$$

(5)

the sparse structure of cuts or connections shown here imposes restrictions on arbitrary variables. Residuals to simplify the model ϵ is considered independent. These are sometimes called innovations, and they are seen as the stochastic transfer of each region from one computation to another.

The reason for this is that, unlike the first one, which shows the goodness of fit from the point of view of each region (we call the cells regions),

the covariance reflects the global behavior of the data, that is, the relationship between the variables. In fact, an objective function optimized by parameters is created from the selected and accepted covariance. by rearranging Eq.

$$\begin{aligned}
 Y(I - \beta) &= \varepsilon \\
 Y &= \varepsilon(1 - \beta)^{-1} \\
 \Sigma &= \langle Y^T Y \rangle \\
 &= (1 - \beta)^{-T} \langle \varepsilon^T \varepsilon \rangle (1 - \beta)^{-1}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{6}$$

This is an example of covariance:

$$S = \frac{1}{n-1} Y^T Y
 \tag{7}$$

If **n** represents the number of samples, the function for maximum likelihood looks like this:

$$F_{ML} = \ln |\Sigma| - tr(S \Sigma^{-1}) -
 \tag{8}$$

Simply put, it is the sample covariance and the variance predicted by the unknown

parameters according to Kullback-Leibler theory. The parameters that minimize this difference are usually estimated using a gradient descent method such as the Newton-Raphson scheme. OLS or ordinary least square method can be used to estimate the initial values (McIntosh and Gonzalez-Lima, 1994).

Based on the peculiarity of the analyzed process, and taking into account that the factors present in the model correspond to the features of the SEM model, it was used.

STEP 1

The data used for the model is mainly collected for the analysis of the factors affecting the activity of existing enterprises in the regions and the growth of their number, which includes the efficiency of the economically active population in the regions, the level of supply of households with clean drinking water, natural gas and electricity, the part of enterprises connected to the Internet, the volume of freight and passenger transportation in the regions and the volume of investments directed to increase the capital size of enterprises by state banks, statistics on population density, which reflect the available resources and their infrastructure in the regions.

3- fig. A visual representation of the ³SEM+ SEM-Path +LCA model

Above picture indicates that the model analyzes the relationship between labor efficiency and the infrastructure affecting it, which is one of

the most important factors of production, and in the next part, an econometric analysis of the impact of labor efficiency and hard and soft

³Statistical analysis software Stata 15 was developed by the author

infrastructure on small business and entrepreneurship are presented.

4- fig. A graphical representation of the relationship between the factors of the ⁴SEM+ SEM-Path +LCA model

Stage II

At this stage, the results obtained will be analyzed. As can be seen from the descriptive model in Figure 5, the covered factors are positively related to each other and the expected results are obtained.

Table-7

Results of SEM model

SEM model	OIM							
	<-	coeff.	std. er.	z	P > z	[95% conf. interval]		
LABORPROD	HOSPITAL	.0886422	.0575046	1.54	0.123	-.0240648	.2013492	
	LCRIME	-10.88273	3.184607	-3.42	0.001	-17.12445	-4.641017	
	LPASSEN	1.645075	1.686748	0.98	0.329	-1.66089	4.951039	
	LGRADUATE	1.018472	1.954219	-0.52	0.602	-4.848671	2.811726	
	DENSITY	.0053744	.0008675	6.20	0.000	.0036742	.0070746	
	GAS	.025896	.0715877	0.36	0.718	-.1662053	.1144132	
	WATER	.4048618	.1274835	3.18	0.001	-.6547249	-.1549988	
	LENERGY	2.112784	.4751778	4.45	0.000	1.181453	3.044116	
	_ cons	114.7989	26.05306	4.41	0.000	63.73584	165,862	

⁴Statistical analysis software Stata 15 was developed by the author

LGBT	<-						
	LABORPROD	.0120332	.0025389	4.74	0.000	.0070572	.0170093
	LNATRES	.0283779	.0213218	1.33	0.183	-.0134121	.0701679
	LFREIGHT	.1123281	.0658909	1.70	0.088	-.0168157	.241472
	INTERNET	.0084658	.0081379	1.04	0.298	-.0244157	.0074841
	INVEST	.0012912	.0094761	0.14	0.892	-.0172817	.0198641
	GAS	.0008004	.0021684	0.37	0.712	-.0050503	.0034495
	WATER	.0115599	.0025149	4.60	0.000	.0066309	.0164889
	LENERGY	.0380384	.0131443	2.89	0.004	-.0638007	-.0122761
	_ cons	7.538834	.6146643	12.26	0.000	6.334115	8.743554
LR test of model saturated :				Chi 2(34) = 418.20,			prob > chi2 =
							0.0000

One of the most important resources of small businesses and private enterprises in the regions is the labor force, and the efficiency of the labor force, in turn, depends on the level of satisfaction of the existing infrastructure created for the labor force. Therefore, the impact of infrastructure on labor force productivity was analyzed. The obtained results showed the expected indicators. Factors such as population density, electricity, and drinking water have a positive and strong impact on labor productivity (the p value of the factors is less than $p > 0.05$).

$$\begin{aligned}
 LABORPROD = & 114.7989_0 \\
 & + .0886422_1 hospital - 10.88273_2 lcrime \\
 & + 1.645075_3 lpassen \\
 & + 1.018472_4 lgraduate \\
 & + .0053744_5 density + .025896_6 gas \\
 & + .4048618_7 water + 2.112784_8 lenergy \\
 & + \mu_i + \delta_i
 \end{aligned}$$

It was found that an increase in the number of crimes in the regions by one unit leads to a decrease in the efficiency of the labor force by a factor of 10 units.

For example, a 1 percent increase in the number of households supplied with electric energy leads to an increase in the number of

K&BT by 2. Independent variables such as transport infrastructure, natural gas, number of graduates, and number of hospitals were found to be positively but weakly related to labor force efficiency (the pi value of the factors is greater than $p < 0.05$). The increase in the number of crimes in the regions had a negative impact on the involuntary variable.

$$\begin{aligned}
 LKBT = & 7.53_0 + .012_1 laborprod \\
 & + .028_2 lnatres \\
 & + .112_3 lfright \\
 & + .008_4 internet \\
 & + .001_5 investment \\
 & + .001_6 gas + .011_7 water \\
 & + .038_8 lenergy + \mu_i + \delta_i
 \end{aligned}$$

At this stage, the econometric analysis of the impact of the existing infrastructure on the number of K&BT enterprises in the regions was continued. As a result of arbitrary factors, if an increase in labor force efficiency by 1 unit leads to an increase in the number of small businesses and entrepreneurial enterprises by 0.12 units, a 1 percent increase in freight turnover and natural resources production leads to an increase in the number of small businesses and entrepreneurial entities by 0.028 percent and 0.112 percent, respectively. was determined. It was determined that increasing the share of households in the

regions with water and gas supply by 1 percent will lead to an increase in the number of small

CONCLUSION

Based on the activities of small business and entrepreneurial units, their past and current status in the region, and the macro-economic conditions of the internal resources and infrastructure of the regions, the regions were evaluated according to criteria such as "low", "medium" and "high".

The feasibility of econometric evaluation and forecasting was based on the development trend of small business and entrepreneurship at the regional level and the infrastructures affecting it, divided into categories such as soft and hard.

In order to increase the level of accuracy of econometric and statistical assessment of the impact of infrastructure on the development of small business and entrepreneurship, especially in the conditions of uneven economic internal resources, factors such as economic infrastructure and social infrastructure affecting the process using the panel evaluation method were used together.

The infrastructure that affects the activity of small business and entrepreneurship in the regions, including the number of enterprises connected to the Internet (X9), households with natural gas (X6), the turnover of goods transported in the regions (X11), and the amount of investments directed by commercial banks to small and medium-sized enterprises (X11) ways to develop prospective scenarios until 2030 in conditions of high accuracy of factors such as distribution and α, β, γ optimal price range.

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